

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

A METHOD OF FORMING A SET OF DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES FOR OPTIMIZING CONTROL PARAMETERS AND DIAGNOSING TECHNICAL SYSTEMS

Hryhorenko Ihor,
Ph. D.

Olkhovikov Dmytro,
National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute", Kharkiv

Piskun Serhii
*Military Institute of Tank Forces of NTU "KhPI",
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

It is substantiated that the control of the state of technical systems is aimed at increasing the reliability of information about the real technical state. An analysis of existing methods of substantiating sets of control parameters of complex technical systems is carried out, their disadvantages and advantages are given. The purpose of the study is to develop a method that allows you to justify the number of control parameters when determining the state of technical systems. The work proposes a method (order) of forming a set of diagnostic features for optimizing control parameters and diagnosing technical systems for assessing their technical condition, which consists of three stages. The basis for the wide use of the proposed method is the hidden potential of multidimensional test signals reflecting a wide range of differences that can be deployed with respect to the generalized control parameter.

Keywords: diagnostics, reliability, control, method, optimization, test signal, technical condition

Problem statement. The functional efficiency of technical systems depends on the timely detection of possible failures. Timely detection of possible failures of technical systems depends on the quality of monitoring and diagnosing their technical condition. Thus, monitoring the condition of technical systems is aimed at increasing the reliability of information about the actual technical condition. The reliability of information about the real technical condition of the system depends on finding the control parameters (diagnostic features) within the limits of possible changes [1, 2]. At the same time, an urgent task is to determine the optimal parameters for monitoring the technical condition of systems to ensure the required level of control reliability and reduce the cost of its control, as this affects the overall operating costs of the system. A suboptimal (irrational) set of control parameters leads to high unproductive costs, reduced control reliability and the efficiency of using technical systems for their intended purpose. The optimal choice of control parameters is one of the most important and complex tasks in the theory of controlling the technical condition of systems [2].

Literature review. A number of methods have been developed to substantiate sets of control parameters for complex technical systems, which are conditionally divided into two groups: expert [1] – [4] and computational [5] – [9].

Expert methods are aimed at determining individual estimates of each parameter of technical systems by experts. The main disadvantage of expert methods is the subjective factor, i.e., a parameter can be assessed by different experts in a very different way. And this can lead to an erroneous conclusion about the "weight" of the control parameter for technical systems

and unreasonable exclusion from the number of controlled parameters of the parameter whose failure, if not detected in time, can lead to failure to fulfill the functional task [2, 3].

Calculation methods include those based on the assessment of various quality indicators of technical systems. Such indicators may include, for example, indicators of element reliability, maintainability, and others [5]. They are based on building a mathematical model of the system and solving the problem of optimizing the composition of control parameters, which depends on the selected optimization criterion [6, 9]. However, contradictions may arise when justifying the composition of control parameters of technical systems. For example, if the cost of controlling parameters with the available means of monitoring and diagnostics exceeds the cost of the technical system sample itself, then the control is economically unprofitable. This is due to the fact that the number of control parameters of technical systems is ambiguously related to the quality indicators of this system. To obtain an optimal solution, a method of sequential approximation is used, which consists in repeatedly solving problems of optimizing the composition of control parameters of technical systems [8].

Calculation methods for selecting control parameters for technical systems also include methods based on solving systems of inequalities that determine the relationship between the obtained and required values of the duration of technical condition monitoring, the cost of monitoring and diagnostic equipment, the frequency of monitoring, and the reliability of false and undetected failures. This group of calculation methods has a major drawback - they do

not take into account the operating parameters of monitoring and diagnostic tools used in the control of technical systems [4], [7].

The purpose of the article is to develop a method that allows to justify the number of control parameters when determining the technical condition of technical systems.

Main part. The analysis of technical systems to control their technical condition is one of the main stages of forming the initial set of diagnostic features that allow developing control and diagnostic programs.

A complex task of monitoring the state of technical systems includes the synthesis of test signals x_i , i.e., a sequence of input vectors $X [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_{m_t}]$, where m_t is the number of test effects on the technical object, to obtain the corresponding output vector $Y(X)$ (output responses $[y_1(x_1), \dots, y_i(x_i), \dots, y_m(x_m)]$). The vector $Y(X)$ provides information about the response of the technical system to the characteristics of the control and diagnostic parameters m , which contain the diagnostic control data (control result) necessary to assess its technical condition. Technical systems are usually complex complexes (objects), so a sequence (algorithm) of diagnostic tests x_i is required to assess their condition and, as a result, determine the presence or absence of faults. Processing of this information (diagnostic control data) allows to assess the state of a technical system and detect a malfunction, i.e., to indicate the location of the malfunction with sufficient accuracy to detect it. Both tasks are solved on the basis of the initial set of diagnostic features for the technical system $y_i(x_i)$. In this case, when determining the optimal set of control parameters n , it is necessary first of all to establish a hierarchy of previously selected parameters m for a particular technical system. To do this, test signals are formulated – the input vector X – and a qualitative analysis of the degree of compliance of the proportions of representation of the elements of the measured parameter by such test signals is carried out. Let us consider the task of processing diagnostic testing data

to monitor the technical condition of a system. The conclusion on the assessment of the technical condition of the system based on the results of monitoring its parameters (diagnostic testing) allows us to make a certain forecast for the future development of state changes and provide recommendations for maintaining its technical condition.

The paper proposes the following method (procedure) for forming a set of diagnostic features to optimize the parameters of control and diagnostics of technical systems to assess their technical condition, consisting of three stages.

In the first stage, taking into account the mathematical model (structural diagram) of the technical system, an initial set of control parameters m is formed, which includes a set of input influences m_t ; reactions to them that reflect the state of the technical system under control. This stage is difficult to formalize. It is necessary to develop general recommendations for the formation of the initial set of diagnostic features that characterize the technical state of the system.

At the second stage, a diagnostic model of the technical system is selected and its characteristics are determined. A diagnostic model is understood as a method of combining (transforming, aggregating) the initial diagnostic features (variants of reactions to the input test signals) to form a generalized diagnostic indicator. There can be many such methods. We propose to use a linear diagnostic model, in which the arrangement of the initial signs is carried out by summing them with certain weights. The initial material for finding the parameters of the diagnostic model is the data of an experimental study of the use of test signals for a diagnostic test of a representative sample of technical system parameters.

It is proposed to use the results of the study by matching the results of monitoring the technical condition of the system for each monitoring parameter (Table 1).

Table 1

Correspondence of the results of technical condition control to the control parameters

Set of parameters m	Impact on the result of technical condition control	Weight of the control parameter	Parameter dependence	Optimum parameters n
x_1	$y_1(x_1)$	0.01	$x_1(x_2)$	–
x_2	$y_1(x_2)$	0.1	$x_2(x_1)$	x_2
...
x_i	$y_i(x_i)$	0.2	–	x_i
...
x_m	$y_m(x_m)$	0.07	–	x_m

The main categories that characterize the structure of the experimental data and are used to determine the optimal parameters of the diagnostic model are the categories of similarity and difference of the rows and columns (control parameters and their results) of the experimental data table. Experimental information has a specific character, so attention should be paid to the description of this specificity and the peculiarities of applying measures of similarity and difference of

objects and features. To determine the parameters of the diagnostic model, it is proposed to use two strategies of empirical and statistical data analysis.

The first strategy is based on the criterion of informativeness of experimental data. This criterion implies that the diagnostic model can be directly determined by approximating the geometric structure, a set of objects in the space of initial features, without using information about empirical (external) influences

on the procedure for controlling technical systems. The use of numerical relations of similarity and difference of objects and features is proposed. A linear diagnostic model (linear approximation) can be built when a significant part of the initial features is highly interconnected (internal consistency) and other features cannot compete with this consistent impact on the structure of data on control parameters. If the internal consistency is due to the reflection of the required technical condition, the parameters of the linear diagnostic model (feature weights) are obtained by the principal component method. If the set of initial features includes several groups of interdependent features, then one or more groups of diagnostic parameters can be combined using factor analysis methods. In this case, useful practical results can be obtained by the method of contrasting groups, which uses the effect of increasing the internal consistency of the initial version of the linear diagnostic model.

The second strategy for determining the parameters of the diagnostic model is based on the involvement and active use of additional initial information about the quality of control as a diagnostic property of the technical system. The criteria by which the training information is formed will be considered the criteria of external informativeness or external criteria. The main components of methods that use external criteria are regression and discriminant analysis methods. It is necessary to describe the types and methods of obtaining training information, as well as provide the necessary information about the classical linear regression and discriminant analysis. It is proposed to consider various modifications of these types of analysis used in diagnostics, taking into account the specifics of experimental measurements. In the future, a piecewise linear diagnostic model will be developed, which is implemented using a typological approach.

The third stage involves standardization and testing of the proposed diagnostic model. It is necessary to develop methods for obtaining standardized diagnostic assessments and consider the main characteristics of the input diagnostic signals used to monitor the technical condition of systems and reflect the quality of the developed diagnostic tool. Automation of solving this task is associated with the use of the basics of the theory of optimization of technical system control parameters. When forming the initial set of features (the initial version of the control parameters m), the entire set of parameters is used. To optimize the control parameters, a specific type of stimulating influences on a technical system is selected and a minimum set of reactions recorded to such influences is formed, which allows to assess the technical condition of the system. Therefore, the formation of the initial set of diagnostic features is important but difficult to formalize. To solve this problem, we offer the following suggestions.

First, it is necessary to conduct a thorough analysis of the technical system assumed as a mathematical model of the diagnostic object.

The method (procedure) of forming the initial diagnostic features to be developed must meet the following requirements:

Sufficiency. The set of initial signs should cover all the selected parameters that characterize the technical condition of the system;

Cost-effectiveness. When developing a set of features, it is necessary to avoid an excessive amount of initial information that may complicate the subsequent empirical and statistical analysis of the parameters of the diagnostic model;

A clear structured system of features. The features should be grouped for a uniform description of the parameters characterizing the technical condition of the system;

Quantitative certainty of the selected features. This certainty is required for empirical and statistical analysis. Features should be expressed in nominal, qualitative or quantitative scales.

These requirements are not exhaustive. When forming a set of diagnostic features, attention should be paid to the methods of optimizing the parameters of control and diagnosis of technical systems. In general, it can be said that the formation of the initial set of features in the design of a new algorithm for monitoring the technical condition is laborious. In fact, another approach to solving the problem of forming initial features is more common, in which such features are elements of known control algorithms. It is proposed to use individual diagnostic features in previously tested objects, to compile a new algorithm from the composition of known methods, and to use the full set of control parameters for multidimensional diagnostic methods as the initial set of features. The advantage of the first approach, where a completely new optimization algorithm is constructed, is that it takes into account the specifics of a particular diagnostic task to the maximum extent possible, which is expressed in a more targeted selection of a set of control parameters, the formulation of individual test signals and their sets. At the same time, the implementation of this approach involves considerable effort in the theoretical development of both the general concept of the mathematical model of the system and many specific details of solving the optimization problem. The second approach does not have the flexibility of the first approach, but avoids the need to solve many specific problems, since it is based on the already tested initial structure of known algorithms for determining a set of control parameters for assessing the technical condition of the system.

Conclusions. The basis for the widespread use of the proposed method is the hidden potential of multidimensional test signals reflecting a wide range of differences, which can be deployed with respect to a new generalized control parameter. Having determined the initial set of features, a variant of the future algorithm for optimizing control parameters is obtained. Further development of this variant is based on the experiment and analysis of its results. Presentation of information about the structure of experimental data using the matrices of relations of control features and their effects on the result of

assessing the technical condition of the system. The number of the optimal set of control parameters n and the number of diagnostic features serves as an intermediate link in the process of building diagnostic models of various types. Regardless, there are two main strategies for determining the parameters of diagnostic models.

Data informativeness exists only in relation to the type of diagnostic model used, the choice of which, in turn, is determined by technical resources and theoretical ideas about the control algorithm. In the diagnostics of complex technical systems, linear models prevail, in which the resultant indicator is presented as a weighted sum of the initial signs. The prevalence of linear models is primarily due to their greatest simplicity, clarity, and ease of solution, which allows, in particular, manual processing of control results. From a mathematical point of view, the development of diagnostics is moving away from linear models. However, they will undoubtedly always be of great practical importance due to their conciseness and good interpretability. In the future, when considering a particular method of determining the parameters of a linear diagnostic model, different terms will be used, but, as noted above, the global attribute for distinguishing these methods is the use or non-use of the criterion of external information content.

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